

Education and Skill Development System of ASEAN+3

S.Chernbumroong¹, V.Jangkrajarn², S.Santiteerakul³, S.Ramingwong^{4*}

^{1,2}*Department of Management and Entrepreneurship, Faculty of Business Administration, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand*

³*Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand*

⁴*Center of Excellence in Logistics and Supply Chain Management, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand*

¹*sainatee.c@cmu.ac.th*, ²*varattaya.j@cmu.ac.th*, ³*salinee.s@cmu.ac.th*,

^{4*}*sakgasem.ramingwong@cmu.ac.th*

Abstract

ASEAN+3 is the collaboration of 10 ASEAN countries with China, Japan, and Korea, aiming at strengthening competitiveness by integrating their economy together. Addressing industry advancement, e.g., Industry 4.0 and globalization, such integration can be challenging. The paper focuses on the human factor by investigating the education and skill development system of ASEAN+3 countries. The assessment is based on 13 related indicators, published in The Global Innovation Index 2018. The result presentation and discussion are divided into 3 areas of the education and skill development system as input, process, and output. The aggregate normalized scores on each area are presented, mapped with GDP per capita of each country. Gaps of the development are then identified, and thus necessary improvements are suggested.

Keywords: Education and skill development system, ASEAN+3

1. Introduction

Education and skill development, as human capital, are the essence to any development. No matter how advanced the technology is, people factor still influences strongly to the betterment [1-5]. The case is invariable for industry, business, or even social development. In the case of interest of the paper, advancement in industry development are highly dependable on this human capital. Human resource management and development are the utmost key success factor in the productivity improvement and financial performance of the firms [6-8]. The significance of the human workforce is arguable since the breakthrough of advanced technology advancement, for example, Artificial Super Intelligence and Cyber-physical system. Yet, the tasks and demands of the workforce may be changed. Yet, humans still play important roles in the jigsaw [9-10].

The study focuses on human capital, starting from education as the preparation of the workforce to the industry. Then, the process of skill development and the output related to the industry are of interest.

The study uses a case study of members of ASEAN+3 countries which comprises 13 strongly-related countries in Asia. With initiatives to integrate the economy together, it is interesting to see if this people factor of each country is aligned despite the big gap in economic strengths. Therefore, in this paper, factors related to the development system of education and skill of ASEAN+3 are investigated if they are commensurate.

2. Background

2.1 ASEAN+3

Association of South East Asian (ASEAN) comprises 10 countries, i.e., Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. In 2003, ASEAN has established an initiative to integrate 10 economies as ASEAN Economic Community or AEC. The aims are to constitute a sustainable and competitive economic region by allowing the free flow of goods, services, investments, and capital within 2020 [11]. ASEAN is a combination of a population of 654.2 million with gross GDP (PPP) of 8.5 trillion USD.

ASEAN also aims to expand economic cooperation with close neighbouring economies, i.e., China, Japan, and South Korea as the ASEAN+3 initiatives. The East Asian Free Trade Area was established with a vision of an East Asian Economic Community [12]. This intra-subregion then expands to a population of 2,247 million with gross GDP (PPP) of 41.5 trillion USD. Today, the intra-region trade is up to 46.8%. The FDI within the region is as much as 50.7% [13].

Today, ASEAN+3 integration has been progressed. However, it is a big challenge where these economies are different in terms of geographic, economic, social, and culture [14]. The size of economies ranges from GDP (PPP) of 35.5 billion USD of Brunei to GDP (PPP) of 25.3 trillion USD of China. Population sizes also range from a country of 0.4 million people to a country of 1,415.0 million people. GDP per capita (PPP) ranges from 4,334.7 USD to 100,344.7 USD. Table 1 summarises the key economic information of ASEAN+3 members.

Table 1. Basic Economical Information of ASEAN+3

Economic Group	Economy	GDP (PPP USD billion)	GDP per capita (PPP USD)	Population (million)	Manufacturing Value Added (% to GDP)	Manufacturing Employment (% working population)
ASEAN	BWN	35.5	79,529.9	0.4	N/A	N/A
	KHM	70.3	4,334.7	16.2	17.6	10.9
	IDN	3,495.9	13,229.5	266.8	21.8	13.5
	LAO	54.9	6,614.5	7.1	N/A	N/A
	MYS	999.8	30,859.9	32.0	23.9	16.5
	MMR	268.3	5,922.0	53.7	N/A	N/A
	PHL	956.0	8,935.9	106.5	22.5	8.3
	SGP	556.2	100,344.7	5.8	18.2	11.1
	THA	1,323.2	19,476.5	69.2	28.7	16.5
	VNM	707.6	7,510.5	96.5	21.0	14.4
+3	CHN	25,313.3	18,109.8	1,415.0	32.1	N/A
	JPN	5,632.5	44,227.2	127.2	18.8	16.2
	KOR	2,139.7	41,350.6	51.2	29.5	17.1

Source: [15, 16]

2.2 Industry in ASEAN+3

ASEAN+3 are industry-based countries. Manufacturing value added to the GDP of ASEAN+3 is averaged at 23.41% [15]. Employment in manufacturing ranges from 8.3 to 17.1%. China, Korea, and Thailand are the top 3 in this case with the manufacturing value-added to GDP ratio of 32.1%, 29.5%, and 28.7%, respectively.

With the current global trend of industrial advancement as the fourth industrial revolution or Industry 4.0, this adds complications to the industry and supply chain integration. Industry 4.0 is a concept that industry utilizes sophisticated technology, such

as Artificial Intelligence, Cyber-physical system, Industrial Internet of Things, to allow the factory and manufacturing system to become smarter. The decision can be made responsively and effectively using real-time data and information that are collected and analysed [17-28].

The industry then should evolve in terms of strategy and operations management. This includes not only technology management but also human resources management. By which the role of the workforce can be changed, human resource development including recruiting and training are to be leveraged with science and technology skills to cope with this industry advancement. The collaboration of industry with university and government is suggested to enhance and improve the competences and skills of the workforce [29].

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Education and Skill Development System

Education and skill development issues can be approached in a vast area and many indicators can be used to reflect the issue, e.g., enrolment, schooling achievement, an infrastructure program, investment, initiatives, etc [3, 30-31]. However, the study selects to use only published, available information to reflect the education and skill development as a system. The framework of input/process/output is used to reflect the issue as follows.

3.2 Assessment Framework

In order to investigate education and skill development system of ASEAN+3, Figure 1 illustrates key indicators used in this paper.

Figure 1. Education and Skill Development System Framework

The investigation is based on the published indicators in The Global Innovation Index 2019 [16]. The report investigates 129 economies using 7 groups of innovation-related factors. Together, there are 80 indicators.

Of interest of the paper is the education and skill development system. Therefore, 13 indicators are selected as the representatives for the case. The paper groups 5 indicators to reflect the input of the education and skill development system as (1) Expenditure on Education, (2) Graduates in Science & Engineering, (3) Researchers, (4) Research Talents in Business, and (5) Knowledge Intensive Employment. Then, 5 indicators are used to reflect the process of education and skill development as (6) Firms offering formal training, (7) Gross Expenditure on R&D, (8) Gross Expenditure on R&D performed by

business, (9) Gross Expenditure on R&D financed by business, and (10) University/industry collaboration. Finally, 3 indicators are used to reflect the output of the system as (11) Scientific & technical articles, (12) Citable document H index, and (13) Growth rate of GDP per person engaged.

4. RESULT PRESENTATION & DISCUSSION

The following section discusses facts and finding on education and skill development system in 3 perspectives, i.e., input, process, and output.

4.1 Education and Skill Development Input

The area focuses on human factors as input to the industry. Expenditure on education reflects the level of government interest in the issue. How good is the education system? What is the success rate of graduation? Besides, how many of these people become researchers in R&D? How many percentages of these researchers are in the business sector? Finally, how many of them in comparison to those unskilled?

Tables 2-4 summarise indicators, their brief description, and source of the data used in the Global Innovation Index report 2019.

Table 2: Indicators for Investigating Education and Skill Development Input (Adapted from [16])

Indicators	Unit	Brief Description	Source	Year
Expenditure on education	% of GDP	Percentages to GDP of the government expenditure on education system. This includes expenditures of all level of government, i.e., local, regional and central. International funds transferred to government are also included.	UNESCO Institute for Statistics	2017
Graduates in science and engineering	% of total tertiary graduates	Percentages to all tertiary graduates of tertiary graduates in science, engineering and related fields	UNESCO Institute for Statistics	2016
Researchers	Full-time equivalent per million population	Number of R&D researchers. Postgraduate PhD students are also included.	UNESCO Institute for Statistics, Eurostat, OECD	2019
Research talent in business enterprise	% per thousand population	Percentage to thousand population of full-time equivalent researchers in the business sector.	UNESCO Institute for Statistics, Eurostat, OECD	2019
Employment in knowledge-intensive services	% of workforce	Percentage to total workforce of managers, professionals and technicians and associates.	International Labour Organization	2018

Figure 2 illustrates an aggregate score of 5 indicators of the education and skill development input, normalizing into a 0-1 range. The score of 1 indicates the best performance in all indicators of interest. The score is then mapped with GDP per capita to realize the economic difference of each country. The linear trend line indicates the average expectation of the score, fitted by the GDP per capita.

Figure 2. Education and Skill Development Input Score

At first, it can be seen that Korea outclasses other ASEAN+3 countries in terms of education and skill development input. Korea is ranked 3rd in the world on researcher density at 7,514.4 researchers per million population. The average number of this indicator of ASEAN+3 is at 2,536 researchers per million population. Korea is also ranked world's 2nd on the percentage of research talent in business enterprise at 81.3%. The average of ASEAN+3 is at 47.2%. From Figure 2, it is clear that Korea also performs much higher than the expectation.

China and Malaysia also perform higher than expected. 67% of researcher in China are classified talent. China is ranked world's 12th in this category. Malaysia is outstanding in science and engineering graduates with a ratio of 32.1%, ranked world's 8th.

Thailand and Philippines are slightly higher than the trendline, indicating an acceptable performance. Whilst research talent ratio in business in Philippines is ranked world's 6th, at 63.2%, the expenditure on education in the country is very low at 2.7% per GDP. The average education expenditure of ASEAN+3 is at 3.88% of GDP.

Japan and Vietnam are lying on the trend line, indicating an expected performance. Despite the high ratio of research talent (73.7%, ranked world's 3rd) and high density of researchers, Japan is weak in expenditure on education at 3.5% of GDP. Vietnam's knowledge-intensive employment is at 1.1%, comparing to the average of ASEAN+3 at 24.5%.

On the other hand, Cambodia, Indonesia, Brunei, and, surprisingly, Singapore perform under what can be expected. Cambodia and Indonesia are weak in expenditure on education, research density, and knowledge-intensive employment. Brunei, in fact, ranks the world's 11th in science and engineering graduates ratio. However, the other areas are lower than the anticipation. Highlighted at Singapore, despite high aggregated score from world's 1st in knowledge-intensive employment (56.1%), world's 5th in graduates in science and engineering (34.5%), and world's 5th in research density (6,729.7 researchers per million population), the expenditure on education is as low as 2.9%. Overall, Singapore's position is under the trend line. This is undesirable.

4.2 Education and Skill Development Process

The area focuses on R&D as the essence of education and skill development. What is the percentage of R&D expenditure? How much does the business enterprise perform R&D and how much does the business enterprise finance R&D? How well the industry collaborates with the university? Also, how many percentage of firms invest in the training program to develop their workers?

Table 3. Indicators for Investigating Education and Skill Development Process (Adapted from [16])

Indicators	Unit	Brief Description	Source	Year
Gross expenditure on R&D (GERD)	% of GDP	Percentage to GDP of gross R&D expenditure	UNESCO Institute for Statistics, Eurostat, OECD	2019
GERD performed by business enterprise	% of GDP	Percentage to GDP of gross R&D expenditure performed by business enterprise	UNESCO Institute for Statistics, Eurostat, OECD	2019
GERD financed by business enterprise	% of total GERD	Percentage to GDP of gross R&D expenditure financed by business enterprise	UNESCO Institute for Statistics, Eurostat, OECD	2019
University/industry research collaboration	[0,100]	Normalized score representing the perceptions to the question: "In your country to what extent do businesses and universities collaborate on research and development (R&D)?"	World Economic Forum	2018
Firms offering formal training	% of firms	Percentage to firms in World Bank's Enterprise Survey sample of firms offering formal training for employees	World Bank	2017

Figure 3. Education and Skill Development Process Score

Figure 3 illustrates the aggregate score of the education and skill development process, mapping with GDP per capita. In this area, Japan, Korea, and China, a +3 group, are superior, performing much higher than the expectation. These 3 countries position world's 1st -3rd in GERD financed by business. The average of these +3 countries is at 77% of total GERD. The average of the ASEAN is at 51.1%. In GERD as % of GDP, Korea, and Japan also rank the world's 2nd and 3rd, respectively. In GERD performed by business as % of GDP, Korea and Japan rank world's 2nd and 5th, respectively. China is the world's 1st in the percentage of firms offering human resource development program, at 79.1%. The average of ASEAN+3 is 32.5%.

Thailand, Malaysia, and Singapore also show promising attainment. Thailand's GERD financed by business is the world's 4th, behind only the + 3 countries. Malaysia and Singapore are outstanding in university/ industry research collaboration.

Oppositely, Indonesia, Cambodia, and Brunei are much under the expectation. Indonesia is weak on R&D expenditure and formal training in firms. Cambodia is weak on R&D expenditure, GERD performed by business, and university/ industry research collaboration. Brunei is also weak in collaboration between university and industry.

4.3 Education and Skill Development Output

The last area focuses on the output of the education and skill development system. The area can be grouped into 2 areas, i.e., academic output and productivity output. The academic output is indicated by the number of scientific and technical journal articles and citable documents H index. The productivity output is indicated by the growth rate of GDP per person engaged.

Table 4. Indicators for Investigating Education and Skill Development Output (Adapted from [16])

Indicators	Unit	Brief Description	Source	Year
Scientific and technical publications	per billion PPP USD GDP	Number of scientific and technical articles published. Only articles in journals covered by the Science Citation Index (SCI) and the Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) are included.	Clarivate Analytics, World Economic Outlook Database	2018
Citable documents H index	H index	H-index expresses article and journal productivity and impact. H-index represents number of articles (H) that have received at least H citations.	SCImago Journal & Country Rank	2019
Growth rate of GDP per person engaged	%	Percentage of 3-year growth rate of GDP per person employed, representing labor productivity	The Conference Board Total Economy Database™ Output	2018

Figure 4. Education and Skill Development Output Score

Interestingly, Figure 4 shows a slight declining relationship of GDP per capita and education and skill development output score. This could lead to further investigation.

However, in general, China, Korea, and Singapore are among the top performers. China is outstanding in labor productivity, reported as the growth rate of GDP per worker. China has a growth rate of 7.1%, ranked 1st in the world. Singapore is also the world's 10th in this criteria, however, the scientific output as the scientific and technical publications is as low as 0.9 articles per billion USD GDP. The average of ASEAN+3 is 7.64 articles per billion USD GDP.

Malaysia, Vietnam, Thailand, and Japan are also considered good in this area. Vietnam has the growth rate of GDP per worker at 6%, ranked world's 3rd. Japan's citable documents H index is also high at 71. The average citable documents H index of ASEAN+3 is at 26.0.

Philippines, Cambodia, Indonesia, and Brunei are otherwise. They are all weak in the scientific and technical publications, at the range of 0.6-3.1 articles per billion USD GDP. Citable documents H index of Brunei and Cambodia are also as low as 1.9 and 4.3, respectively. However, Cambodia and Philippines are both outstanding in the growth rate of GDP per worker at 4.9%, ranked world's 9th and 10th.

5. DISCUSSION

Figure 5 summarises key findings from the investigation. It can be found that, in general, China and Korea are the top two countries performing over expectations in all areas of education and skill development system of ASEAN+3. Singapore and Japan also perform well in process and output areas, respectively. Comparatively, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, and Philippines moderately perform in all areas. Oppositely, Indonesia, Cambodia, and Brunei perform under expectation.

Figure 5. Performance of ASEAN+3 in Education and Skill Development System

6. CONCLUSION

The study investigated the education and skill development system of ASEAN+3 countries using 13 indicators, published in The Global Innovation Index 2019. In terms of education and skill development input, Korea is the best performer with high potential in research density and research talent. China and Malaysia are also among the leading tier. Oppositely, Cambodia, Indonesia, Brunei, and Singapore are among those who need improvement. Singapore, despite high score from the number of researchers and graduates and knowledge-intensive employment rate, performs lower than expectation. In terms of education and skill development process, Japan, Korea, and China are top performers with high business R&D investment. Indonesia, Cambodia, and Brunei are otherwise. In terms of output, China, Korea, and Singapore are among the top performer, outstanding in labor productivity. Oppositely, Philippines, Cambodia, Indonesia, and Brunei are among the least productive in terms of academic output.

The information presented here is only suggestive, not conclusive, due to the limited resource of data and information. However, it reflects gaps in many perspectives if these countries are to be aligned in industry development.

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Authors

Dr. Sainatee Chernbumroong is a full-time lecturer at the department of Management and Entrepreneurship, Faculty of Business Administration, Chiang Mai University, Thailand.

Dr. Varattaya Jangkrajarn is an assistant professor at the department of Management and Entrepreneurship, Faculty of Business Administration, Chiang Mai University, Thailand.

Dr. Salinee Santiteerakul is a full-time lecturer at the department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Chiang Mai University, Thailand.

Dr. Sakgasem Ramingwong is an associate professor and the deputy head of the Center of Excellence in Logistics and Supply Chain Management, Chiang Mai University, Thailand.